

Proposal for Participation in Nordes Summer School 2024

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Data, data, data! Everything seems to be revolving around data. Disguised with the promise of a better life, companies are racing to collect, store, sell, and make sense of data for economic benefit through the logics of *surveillance capitalism* (Zuboff, 2019). Through narratives that draw a straight line from data to progress, the efforts to keep users hooked on data-intensive things to generate more behavioural data are justified, leaving not much room to critique the impact of post-digital era on societies, communities, professions, as well as on nature and climate.

The experience of digital technologies through screens almost magically falling from the ‘clouds’, deceits users into thinking they are immaterial. However, as Kate Crawford and Vladan Joler (2018), illustrate with the Anatomy of an AI System, and Kate Crawford (2021) elaborately discuss in Atlas of AI, these technologies on the contrary rely heavily on natural resources in addition to human labor.

As digital technologies especially based on artificial intelligence (AI) become more pervasive, their destruction of nature through the extraction of minerals, data centers that consume energy and water, and the growing e-waste, will exponentially grow. As a result, their negative impacts on the climate as well as the communities whose livelihoods depend on these lands, will grow, and become more explicit. However, despite the recent interest in the extensive consumption of natural resources by AI systems, there is still no concrete work in the domains of governance or infrastructures that acknowledges the agency of nature as well as demands accountability and affirmative regenerative action.

In my PhD project I resist to the progress narrative created for data-intensive things and AI by using Terms of Service (ToS) as an entry point since ToS and its accompanying policies are quite central in facilitating and legitimising data practices through technical and legal language that seemingly comply with the legal frameworks and regulations (Özçetin & Wiltse, 2023). Through *designerly ways of reading*, a methodology I am developing that is based on moving in-between boundaries, times, scales, and mediums, I start to reveal the entangled ecosystem of relations hidden in plain sight in data-intensive things (Özçetin & Wiltse, 2023). Additionally, I disorientate towards design histories, when similar struggles resulting from the changing dynamics of production and consumption, and design and use, took place, with an idea to reorientate (Özçetin & Redström, 2024; Redström & Wiltse, 2019).

Engaging with posthuman theories and more-than-human practices, I ask how we can form, sustain, and break relations with data intensive things in post digital era that better distribute power and control not only among humans but also among more-than-human entities considering the absence of nature in these policies (Özçetin & Özçetin, 2023; Özçetin & Wiltse, 2023;). Through design explorations I not only reveal these issues but also intend to imagine alternative governance and economic models, infrastructures, and ethical frameworks for *Terms of Radiance*, a state of radiating collective happiness in creating and sustaining relations with data-intensive things.

Through my participation at Nordes Summer School, I hope to improve my positioning within the existing work, shape my design explorations, and contribute to the group by offering a topic that is not much explored within design.

Acknowledgements

We acknowledge the Sami people of Ubmeje Sápmi, the land on which we now partly live and work. We pay our respect to past, present and future Custodians and Elders and their continuing cultural, spiritual, and educational practices. We also pay our respects to land, water, and air that sustain life.

This work is supported by the project DCODE. This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955990.

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